

Article Title: The use of new Refrigerants to Combat Climate Change

Refrigerants are a crucial part of medicine. Many medical devices, from disinfectants to organ preservers, all use refrigerators to keep the components clean until use. However, many people don't know how much harm these revolutionary devices have caused to the world. However, a new formula for a refrigerant that I created may be able to solve this issue.

But first, it's crucial to understand the use of a refrigerant in refrigerators. Refrigerants are the liquid that runs the whole refrigerator and what produces the cooling effect. The fridge cools down the refrigerant for it to take away heat from the inside of the refrigerator. The refrigerant is then heated up and depressurized for being reused in the system again, as shown in Figure 1.1. This system's energy efficiency varies based on the refrigerant's boiling point. The first home electric refrigerator was made by Fred W. Wolf in 1913, but it didn't start to get popular until William C. Durant made the first refrigerator which contained the compressor inside. By 1927, refrigerators were in widespread use all over the US. In 1928, Freons were invented, which were a group of multiple refrigerants, most prominently CFC-12 and HCFC-22. Until the 1970s, Freons were the main refrigerants in use for commercial systems. Their incredible energy efficiency rates gave them the edge over all their competitors. They remain, to date, the most efficient refrigerant.

Figure 1.1: A diagram of a compression refrigerator, which is the most used model today.

But while companies and consumers were happily cooling all their equipment and soft drinks, they didn't realize how big of a problem this was. Freons were slowly

chipping away at the ozone layer because of their high ODPs (ozone depletion potential). At an August 1985 meeting of scientists, NASA scientist Pawan Bhartia showed satellite images of the Earth taken from space. These photos revealed a huge gap in the ozone layer over Antarctica. In what is considered a big success in international policymaking, countries from all over the world met and made the Montreal Protocol, a plan to limit ozone depletion which was signed unanimously. A shocking 34 out of the 72 ODP gases were used as refrigerants at the time, and they were a primary factor in the forming of the ozone hole. In the 1990s CFC-12, a potent Freon, was banned from production in the US along with other refrigerants. As more and more refrigerants started getting banned, companies switched to what they thought were better alternatives. They didn't realize that these so-called "eco-friendly" refrigerants were just as bad for the environment in a different way.

These refrigerants were, in fact accelerating global warming by acting as greenhouse gases. Their high Global Warming Potential (GWP) was contributing to the rises in temperatures. In 2016, the UN met yet again to fix their previous mistake. The Kigali Amendment was a plan to reduce emissions by phasing out different refrigerants and making countries reduce their use of air conditioning. In 2020, HCFC-22, another Freon, was banned for use in the US, along with a myriad of other refrigerants. In 2013, the American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers created a classification system for refrigerants based on safety hazards. There are two measures for this standard: flammability and toxicity, as shown in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2: A diagram showing the different ASHRAE classifications of refrigerants

At this point, we come to the present, where refrigerant companies are making solutions that are truly better for the environment, and it seems like the environment is going to be fine. But this just isn't true. Even if countries meet all these deadlines, in a realistic scenario, global temperatures will rise by at least 1.3 degrees Celsius, according to SSP2 (Shared Socioeconomic Pathways). To put this into perspective, a rise of 0.5 degrees Celsius means that sea levels will rise by about 6 inches, putting many cities at

risk. At the current rate, by 2100, parts of Queens and Brooklyn in New York will be submerged.

So now comes the need for a much better solution to this. After research on the best refrigerants to use, I have come up with a formula that not only is on par with Freons in terms of efficiency but is also the most eco-friendly refrigerant of its time. This new refrigerant is called Solareon. It is a mix of 62.9% R-744(CO₂) and 37.1% HFO-1336mzz-Z (Chemical formula C₄F₆). Don't be worried when you hear that Solareon contains CO₂. Compared to other refrigerants, CO₂ is much better for the environment because of its low GWP of 1 and ODP of 0. The reason people have a bad opinion of it is because it is used so much. However, relative to other refrigerants, CO₂ is a great option. HFO-1336mzz-Z has a GWP of 2 and an ODP of 0. The main reason this refrigerant is included is to make the boiling point as energy efficient as possible. Solareon has a GWP of 1.4 and an ODP of 0, much lower than any other viable competitors. Solareon's main competitors are R-1234yf, which has a GWP of 4; however, it is not as efficient in terms of boiling point. It also has a GWP of 4, which is approximately 3 times more than Solareon. Finally, since it's a B2L refrigerant, it's toxic and (mildly) flammable, which are serious safety hazards. On the other end of the spectrum, Freon, which has approximately the same energy efficiency statistics and has the coveted A1 status, would absorb 2800 times more heat than Solareon; this would mean that global warming would accelerate by over 3,000 times compared to Solareon's impact on the environment. Another useful quality of Solareon is that it is also a Class A1 refrigerant, which means that it is completely unhazardous, which almost no environmentally safe refrigerant has managed to achieve. It is compatible with Freon systems, which means that some old refrigerators can be reused with this refrigerant. Solareon is a much better alternative than all its competitors, both in terms of energy efficiency and sustainability.

The medical industry can benefit greatly from Solareon. It can make sure that when nurses refrigerate equipment, they are making a difference in the environment for the better by using this system. This new refrigerant is amazing for the medical industry because of its extremely low flash point, meaning that it is versatile in many environments and conditions.

As the world continues to worry about climate change, it's extremely important to switch to better refrigerant alternatives. This new refrigerant is a very viable alternative to cut down global warming levels and can be used in a variety of applications to also help the medical field.

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